

Strictly Local Functions Are Simply Typed

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Abstract

Strictly local functions provide a formal account of the intuitive notion of locality, where a process applies up to some domain. The locality is that of immediate adjacency, which is reminiscent of iterative processes. Naturally, one wonders what exactly the algorithmic characteristics of strictly local functions are. Unfortunately, both the automata-theoretic and model-theoretic formalizations do not reflect a direct implementation. This paper argues that strictly local functions, when directly implemented using a functional approach, are simply typed in the sense of simple type theory (as opposed to dependent type theory). The simple types correspond to quantifier-free logical formulae, thus connecting the computational side to the logical side.

1 Introduction

Since Kaplan and Kay (1994), regular models have proved to be a useful tool in the formalization of phonological rules due to their relatively weak computational complexity. Recently, subregular models, that is, models even weaker than regular models, have been shown to be feasible in phonological descriptions (Rogers and Pullum, 2011). Among them, *strictly local functions* incorporate the intuitive notion of locality into the otherwise non-local regular models (Chandlee, 2014).¹ Logically, they correspond to quantifier-free logical transductions, since quantifiers allow the encoding of global information (Chandlee and Jardine, 2019, 2021).

Two radically different formalizations have been used to define strictly local functions. The model-theoretic approach defines them in terms of functions from models to models, where a model encodes a representation with a finite domain of elements and a collection of functions and relations on

¹In this paper, strictly local functions are “non-recursive”, therefore excluding the so-called output strictly local functions.

the domain. Informally speaking, the finite domain of elements act as indexes in a representation, the functions manipulate the indexes in some way (typical examples include predecessor and successor functions), and the relations describe the “shape” of the representation. Strictly local functions are then encoded as property-preserving mappings between models. This is a denotational approach that in the author’s opinion lacks intuition. For one thing, it is not very clear how to directly derive an implementation from such an approach.

The automata-theoretic approach, on the other hand, is a more operational approach. It is well-known that regular models relate to finite-state machines, which are machines with a finite number of states and therefore transitions between states. Strictly local functions, in particular, are *deterministic* finite-state machines with locality constraints on state transitions. Such machines, nonetheless, are *abstract* machines that require some form of compilation, manually or mechanically, to implement. They are closer to an algorithmic understanding than mappings between models are, but they are not algorithms per se. Importantly, they do not directly encode the locality constraints.

Instead, this paper proposes a functional approach, namely an approach that utilizes the usual functional programming techniques. Specifically, a functional implementation of strictly local functions is given, which can be directly implemented in any conventional programming language capable of functional programming. Some of its properties are discussed and related to a *simple type theory* under Howard’s ([1969] 1980) formulae-as-types interpretation. This paper argues that strictly local functions, and correspondingly the parameter step functions, are simply typed as opposed to dependently typed. This idea resonates with the quantifier-free logical characterization. Moreover, such an interpretation connects the computational side to the logical side, providing us with a unified

$$\begin{array}{c}
\overline{F([a_1, \dots, a_{k-1}]) = [b_1, \dots, b_{k-1}]} \text{ INIT}^k \\
\overline{F([\dots, a_1, \dots, a_{k-1}]) = [\dots, b_1, \dots, b_{k-1}] \quad f(a_1, \dots, a_k) = b_k} \text{ ITER-L}^k \\
\overline{F([\dots, a_1, \dots, a_{k-1}, a_k]) = [\dots, b_1, \dots, b_{k-1}, b_k]} \\
\overline{f(a_1, \dots, a_k) = b_1 \quad F([a_2, \dots, a_k, \dots]) = [b_2, \dots, b_k, \dots]} \text{ ITER-R}^k \\
\overline{F([a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, \dots]) = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_k, \dots]}
\end{array}$$

Figure 1: A direct implementation of strictly k -local functions

conceptual framework to reason about computational complexity.

2 A Functional Approach

2.1 The Implementation

The intuition of strictly k -local functions is that they *iterate* left-to-right (or right-to-left), “remembering” a part of previously processed inputs up to a finite k window, and use that in combination of the current input to decide the output.² The outputs are, at the end, collected in a certain manner, say string concatenation. This should remind us of the notion of *fold* in the sense of Hutton (1999), with an operator that manipulates the state in a strictly local manner.

Indeed, Figure 1 is a direct implementation that can be converted to such a *fold*. The INIT rule simply initiates the iteration by finitely mapping a sequence (written with brackets) of length $k - 1$ to another sequence. This can also be itself viewed as a strictly $(k - 1)$ -local function with a restricted domain. The ITER-L or ITER-R rule is responsible for the actual iteration, parameterized by a step function f .³ The step function accepts the “remembered” inputs along with the current input, and returns an output to be prepended/appended to the output sequence. The two rules in combination generate the set of output sequences as desired.⁴

Definition 1. A *strictly local function* F is defined by the derivations consisting of INIT and *either* ITER-L or ITER-R, parameterized by a *step function* f .

Due to the non-recursive nature of the implementation, directionality of iteration should be irrelevant in some sense. There are, in fact, two notions

²Where the context makes it clear, the factor k is omitted.

³Indeed, the INIT rule can also be thought of as parameterized by a function. It is stated as an axiom here for simplicity.

⁴We abstract away from the exact type of sequence to allow a monoidal fold to further process it, which in turn can be “fused” into the strictly local function.

of such irrelevance that can be defined.⁵

Theorem 1. Two strictly local functions F and F' parameterized by the same step function f are equivalent modulo INIT, that is, the equivalence classes formed by identifying resulting sequences with different INIT parts are isomorphic.

Proof. By induction on the length of the sequence. Assume a sequence of an appropriate length, and prepend (or append) to the sequence. The trick for the case of different directionality is realizing that each equivalence class corresponds to a pair of prefix (or suffix) and the set of all possible INIT parts, where the latter is fixed for any F . \square

This is not a very intuitive notion of irrelevance, because it says that all strictly local functions parameterized by the same step function f are equivalent “to the limit”, but we are not even close to such a limit in natural language. To put it in a diagram, the case of different directionality works as

$$\begin{array}{rcccc}
\text{Output} & \text{INIT} \dots & b_1 \dots b_m & \dots \dots \\
\text{Input} & \dots \dots & a_1 \dots a_m & \dots \dots \\
\text{Output}' & \dots \dots & b_1 \dots b_m & \dots \text{INIT}'
\end{array}$$

In particular, the INIT parts are usually critical, because they are boundary-adjacent. To account for this, a more subtle notion of irrelevance can be defined. To do so, an auxiliary definition is needed.

Definition 2. A *boundary-enriched* sequence for a strictly k -local function is produced by prepending and appending k boundaries to the sequence, where the boundary is an arbitrary chosen element not in the input type.

To be sure, the only reason we need boundaries is to abuse the fact that boundaries can be used for indexing purpose.⁶

⁵A remark should be made that the “irrelevance” depends on the fact that the fold is monoidal.

⁶The more traditional use of boundaries, namely to delimit the domain of application, is discussed in Chan (2023).

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{F([\sigma]) = [\sigma] \quad f(\sigma, \sigma) = \sigma}{F([\sigma, \sigma]) = [\sigma, \sigma] \quad f(\sigma, \sigma) = \sigma} \\
\frac{F([\sigma, \sigma]) = [\sigma, \sigma] \quad f(\sigma, \sigma) = \sigma}{F([\sigma, \sigma, \sigma]) = [\sigma, \sigma, \sigma]} \\
\frac{F([\acute{\sigma}]) = [\sigma] \quad f(\acute{\sigma}, \sigma) = \acute{\sigma}}{F([\acute{\sigma}, \sigma]) = [\sigma, \acute{\sigma}] \quad f(\sigma, \sigma) = \sigma} \\
\frac{F([\acute{\sigma}, \sigma]) = [\sigma, \acute{\sigma}] \quad f(\sigma, \sigma) = \sigma}{F([\acute{\sigma}, \sigma, \sigma]) = [\sigma, \acute{\sigma}, \sigma]} \\
\frac{F([\sigma]) = [\sigma] \quad f(\sigma, \acute{\sigma}) = \sigma}{F([\sigma, \acute{\sigma}]) = [\sigma, \sigma] \quad f(\acute{\sigma}, \sigma) = \acute{\sigma}} \\
\frac{F([\sigma, \acute{\sigma}]) = [\sigma, \sigma] \quad f(\acute{\sigma}, \sigma) = \acute{\sigma}}{F([\sigma, \acute{\sigma}, \sigma]) = [\sigma, \sigma, \acute{\sigma}]}
\end{array}$$

Figure 2: Three derivations for bounded tone shift in Rimi

Lemma 1. *Finite maps on sequences of length k are embedded in strictly $(k + 1)$ -local functions on boundary-enriched sequences of length $3k$.*

Proof. By construction. Note that boundaries are used for indexing purpose by counting the number of boundaries in the remembered inputs. \square

More precisely, each finite map is isomorphic to a “boundary-agnostic” equivalence class of such strictly local functions. From this lemma, the notion of irrelevance can be derived.

Theorem 2. *From a strictly local function F , the strictly local function F' of opposite directionality can be defined on boundary-enriched sequences.*

Proof. By construction. INIT defines a finite map, which is subject to Lemma 1. Combine this with Theorem 1 by combining the step functions. By definition, the step function f for F must not be aware of boundaries. \square

Apparently, there is still a matter of naturalness in the decision of directionality, since one or the other does not require boundaries to be present. If boundaries are *always* present, the choice of INIT simply does not matter, and Theorem 1 suffices. However, it seems more natural for the choice of INIT to be significant.

The correctness of the implementation is by construction. The usual formulation of strict locality is that given a $k - 1$ prefix/suffix, the set of output heads/tails must be fixed. In other words, the output must not depend on any information out of the k window. It is easy to see how the implementation encodes this idea.

2.2 Example: Rimi

To put the implementation in use, consider bounded tone shift in Rimi (Meyers, 1997). For comparison, the analysis mirrors that in Chandlee and Jardine

(2021). The trisyllabic cases can be abstracted as the finite map

$$\begin{array}{l}
\sigma\sigma\sigma \mapsto \sigma\sigma\sigma \\
\acute{\sigma}\sigma\sigma \mapsto \sigma\acute{\sigma}\sigma \\
\sigma\acute{\sigma}\sigma \mapsto \sigma\sigma\acute{\sigma}
\end{array}$$

In other words, a high tone is realized on a syllable whenever the preceding syllable bears a high tone *in the input sequence*. The step function is a simple one.⁷

$$\begin{array}{l}
f(\sigma, _) := \sigma \\
f(\acute{\sigma}, \sigma) := \acute{\sigma} \\
f(\acute{\sigma}, \acute{\sigma}) := ? \quad (\text{absent case})
\end{array}$$

Combine this with a constant INIT such that $F([_]) = [\sigma]$, we have the three derivations in Figure 2 as desired. The reader is welcome to verify that both notions of irrelevance apply, although only the boundary-enriched one makes sense in this specific analysis, as expected.⁸

3 A Type-Theoretic Perspective

3.1 Simple Type Theory

The simple type theory, in the narrow sense, refers to the type theory introduced in Church (1940) for the λ -calculus, which consists of two base types and a function type constructor. This is also the familiar one as used in the Montagovian tradition of formal semantics. Simple type theory, in a general sense, refers to any type theory without dependent types, contrasting with the famous type theory of Martin-Löf ([1973] 1975) and subsequent ones.

⁷Following the convention in functional programming, the underscore ($_$) is a wildcard pattern that matches anything. The functions are defined in an equational style, assuming that patterns are exhaustive and matched in the apparent order.

⁸If a potential final high tone is assumed to stay intact, however, boundary-enriching the input sequence from the get-go is necessary.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash x : A} \text{VAR} \\
\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash e : B}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x. e : A \rightarrow B} \text{FUN-I} \qquad \frac{\Gamma \vdash f : A \rightarrow B \quad \Gamma \vdash a : A}{\Gamma \vdash f a : B} \text{FUN-E} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash a : A \quad \Gamma \vdash b : B}{\Gamma \vdash (a, b) : A \times B} \text{PROD-I} \qquad \frac{\Gamma \vdash p : A \times B}{\Gamma \vdash \text{proj}_1 p : A} \text{PROD-E}_1 \qquad \frac{\Gamma \vdash p : A \times B}{\Gamma \vdash \text{proj}_2 p : B} \text{PROD-E}_2 \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash a : A}{\Gamma \vdash \text{inj}_1 a : A + B} \text{SUM-I}_1 \qquad \frac{\Gamma \vdash b : B}{\Gamma \vdash \text{inj}_2 b : A + B} \text{SUM-I}_2 \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash u : A + B \quad \Gamma, x : A \vdash l : C \quad \Gamma, y : B \vdash r : C}{\Gamma \vdash \text{match } u \mid x.l \mid y.r : C} \text{SUM-E}
\end{array}$$

Figure 3: A simply-typed λ -calculus and its judgments

Simple type theory, although not as powerful as dependent type theory, is important exactly because it is not as powerful. This is especially important given our task of finding a restrictive computational model. Under Howard’s ([1969] 1980) formulae-as-types interpretation, simple type theory corresponds to first-order propositional logic.⁹ This means that we have neither quantifiers in the predicate-logical sense, nor in the propositional-logical sense (unlike in the system F (Girard, [1970] 1971, 1972)¹⁰). A simply-typed λ -calculus suitable for our purposes is given in Figure 3. It consists of three type constructors, namely function (\rightarrow), product (\times), and sum ($+$). Introduction and elimination rules are given for each constructor, which should remind the reader of the corresponding logical rules. Formation rules for terms and types are omitted, but they are straightforward to figure out. Structural rules are omitted for lack of interest. Computation rules are the usual ones, namely β -reduction for functions, products, and sums.

A salient feature of this system is that types themselves are *propositions*, making the typed λ -terms *proofs*.¹¹ In a judgment of the form $\Gamma \vdash t : \tau$, the term t has type τ in the *context* Γ , where the context in this case is a typing environment, that is, a finite map from variables to their types. The con-

text is therefore a set of assumptions that certain propositions hold, where the variables are eventually substituted with the proofs. This gives us a notion of provability.

Definition 3. The type τ is *inhabited* iff there is a term t of type τ in the empty context.

An inhabited type is a provable proposition, and the typed term is a proof of the proposition. The term can be further subject to computation rules, which normalize proofs. In the end, the resulting system is exactly Prawitz’s (1965) theory of *natural deduction*.

Apparently, some axioms introducing constants and related introduction rules are needed if we want to prove anything useful at all. Data type declarations in programming languages can be viewed as such. For example, Peano’s formulation of natural numbers consists of an axiom and an introduction rule.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\Gamma \vdash \text{zero} : \text{Nat}} \text{ZERO} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash n : \text{Nat}}{\Gamma \vdash \text{succ } n : \text{Nat}} \text{SUCC}
\end{array}$$

Inductive types and their properties are out of the scope of this paper. We are interested in basic constants, with which we can talk about strictly local functions. Alternatively, we can also assume a non-empty context, which is nothing more than a set of named constants.

3.2 Typing Strictly Local Functions

Strictly local functions as in Figure 1 are not well-typed. The reason is that a strictly k -local function is only defined for sequences of length n where $n \geq k - 1$. To circumvent this problem, we need a more precise type.

⁹This may sound weird to those who are more familiar with the set-theoretic tradition of logic, but it is useful to think that λ -abstraction corresponds to a concept of “quantification” (over *proofs*!) different than that in predicate logic. Confusingly, “order” is a loaded term (over *what*?).

¹⁰ F has a *polymorphic* type theory, which is related to the notion of polymorphism. In short, type abstraction allows “quantification” over propositions.

¹¹For an accessible introduction to this principle, refer to Wadler (2015).

How do we type a sequence whose length is at least k ? The idea is very simple. From such a sequence we can extract a prefix/suffix of length k , because it must have at least that much elements. To type a “sequence” of a fixed length k , we simply use a product type $\tau_1 \times \cdots \times \tau_k$.¹²

Definition 4. A sequence of a fixed length k ($k \geq 1$) can be converted to a k -tuple of type $\tau_1 \times \cdots \times \tau_k$ by the metafunction \mathcal{T} , defined as

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{T}[[a_1]] &:= a_1 \\ \mathcal{T}[[a_1, a_2, \dots]] &:= (a_1, \mathcal{T}[[a_2, \dots]])\end{aligned}$$

The inductive definition of k -tuples is omitted, but it should be straightforward to derive. Then, a sequence with at least k elements can be represented as a pair of a k -tuple for the prefix/suffix and a sequence with the remaining elements.

We also need a type for the elements. All we care about in a strictly local function is terminal symbols, and each terminal symbol can be treated as a basic constant from the view of the strictly local function.¹³ An element therefore has a sum type $\tau_1 + \cdots + \tau_k$ given an alphabet with k terminal symbols. As an example, if the alphabet specifies three terminal symbols a, b, c , an element has type $a + b + c$. Here, the symbols themselves are used as types; the terms are unimportant (and *cannot* be important; see footnote 13) to the strictly local function.¹⁴

The definition of strictly local functions needs to be changed to fit in the types. The change is minimal—just split the sequence into a pair—and therefore not shown here. A parameter step function takes k elements and therefore has type $(\tau \times \cdots \times \tau) \rightarrow \tau'$, where τ is the input type and τ' is the output type. Similarly, a strictly k -local function as a whole has type $(\tau \times \cdots \times \tau) \times [\tau] \rightarrow (\tau' \times \cdots \times \tau') \times [\tau']$, where $[\tau]$ is a homogeneous sequence type. Now we see how strictly local functions are simply typed.

3.3 Example: Rimi

The Rimi example in Section 2.2 is reused here as a quick example. Recall that bounded tone shift in

¹²Obviously, there can be many isomorphic types due to the associativity of products (similarly for sums). They are taken to be right associative per convention.

¹³It does *not* matter what the elements *really* are, because we are dealing with abstract data. It suffices that they are accordingly typed.

¹⁴The symbols therefore also stand for injected terms as a notational convenience.

Rimi is a strictly 2-local function. The input type is $\sigma + \acute{\sigma}$, while the output type is $\sigma + \acute{\sigma} + ?$.

This is also a good place to show how the equational, pattern-matching definition can be compiled to a λ -term.¹⁵ We consider a decision tree, where each variant of an element is a branch, and each element is a level. The tree is

Given this tree, we can derive the λ -term for the step function, which is¹⁶

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda(a_1, a_2). \\ \text{match } a_1 \mid _ . \sigma \mid _ . (\text{match } a_2 \mid _ . \acute{\sigma} \mid _ . ?)\end{aligned}$$

where, provided p is not free in e ,

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda(x, y). e := \\ \lambda p. (\lambda x. (\lambda y. e) (\text{proj}_2 p)) (\text{proj}_1 p)\end{aligned}$$

We can apply this to an example term and see that it indeed reduces to the correct term.

$$\begin{aligned}(\lambda(a_1, a_2). \text{match } a_1 \mid \dots \mid \dots) (\acute{\sigma}, \sigma) \\ \rightarrow \text{match } (\text{proj}_1 (\acute{\sigma}, \sigma)) \mid \dots \mid \dots \\ \rightarrow \text{match } \acute{\sigma} \mid \dots \mid \dots \\ \rightarrow \text{match } (\text{proj}_2 (\acute{\sigma}, \sigma)) \mid _ . \acute{\sigma} \mid _ . ? \\ \rightarrow \text{match } \sigma \mid _ . \acute{\sigma} \mid _ . ? \\ \rightarrow \acute{\sigma}\end{aligned}$$

that is, $f(\acute{\sigma}, \sigma) = \acute{\sigma}$.

3.4 Generalized Output Types

So far, we have considered output types that are simple sum types of base types. Our simple type theory, however, allows more generalized output types. For example, strictly local function can be used to recognize whether a sequence is valid by setting the output type to a Boolean type, and the resulting sequence is then folded under conjunction. Actually, a Boolean type is nothing more than a sum type $\top + \perp$.

¹⁵The compilation of pattern matching is an interesting topic in its own; see Maranget (2008) for the decision tree-based approach.

¹⁶More realistically, the match branches can be tone deletion and assignment operations.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\tau <: \tau} \text{REFL} \\
\frac{\tau_a <: \tau_b \quad \tau_b <: \tau_c}{\tau_a <: \tau_c} \text{TRANS} \\
\frac{}{\tau <: \tau + \tau'} \text{SUM-R}_1 \\
\frac{\tau_l <: \tau_r}{\tau_l + \tau' <: \tau_r + \tau'} \text{MONO-L} \\
\frac{}{\tau <: \tau' + \tau} \text{SUM-R}_2 \\
\frac{\tau_l <: \tau_r}{\tau' + \tau_l <: \tau' + \tau_r} \text{MONO-R}
\end{array}$$

Figure 4: A subtyping relation on sum types

Those who are familiar with functional programming should know that a sum type can be used as an “either” type. Given two types τ_a and τ_b , the sum type $\tau_a + \tau_b$ means “either τ_a or τ_b ”, and match can be used to discriminate the two. It is apparent that Boolean types are embedded in either types, given the term $\lambda u. \text{match } u \mid _ . \top \mid _ . \perp$. More precisely, converting to a Boolean type means dropping either this or that proof, therefore losing information.

Another way to understand this is that a strictly local function can be used to “repair” a sequence to fit into the target language. To do this, the either type $\tau_a + \tau_b$ is understood to be composed of an “as-is” type τ_a and a “repaired” type τ_b . Recognizing functions of type $\tau \rightarrow \top + \perp$ are embedded in repairing functions of type $\tau \rightarrow \tau_a + \tau_b$.

Surprisingly, transducing functions are also embedded in repairing functions. Actually, this is not surprising if we consider the “collapsing” of sum types. To define the notion of collapsing, we first need a notion of subtyping on sum types, defined as in Figure 4. This notion of subtyping leads to embedding.¹⁷

Lemma 2. *For any two sum types τ_a and τ_b , if $\tau_a <: \tau_b$, τ_a is embedded in τ_b .*

Proof. By induction on the derivation of $\tau_a <: \tau_b$. The REF and TRANS cases trivially follow from the properties of embedding. \square

Collapsing a sum type means flattening it and, importantly, deduplicating the base types.

Definition 5. A sum type can be *collapsed* by the metafunction \mathcal{C} , defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{C}[(\tau_a + \tau_b) + \tau_c] &:= \mathcal{C}[\tau_a + \tau_b + \tau_c] \\
\mathcal{C}[\tau_a + \tau_b] &:= \begin{cases} \mathcal{C}[\tau_b] & \text{if } \tau_a <: \mathcal{C}[\tau_b] \\ \tau_a + \mathcal{C}[\tau_b] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\
\mathcal{C}[\tau] &:= \tau
\end{aligned}$$

Finally, the desired embedding can be stated. Note that for any repairing function whose output

¹⁷It can be complemented by a notion of type equivalence, which leads to isomorphism.

element type is τ , the transducing function whose output element type is $\mathcal{C}[\tau]$ can be defined.

Theorem 3. *For any sum type τ , $\mathcal{C}[\tau]$ is embedded in τ .*

Proof. By induction on the size of τ . Consider the cases where the left summand is and is *not* another sum type. Use Lemma 2 where necessary. \square

3.5 Example: Standard Chinese

A concrete example can be given to show what this entails. In Standard Chinese, the alveolo-palatal affricates/fricative must appear before high vowels, while the alveolar ones appear complementarily.¹⁸ Mirroring Duanmu’s (2007) analysis, this can be analyzed as a single series of alveolar affricates/fricative coupled with the finite map

$$\begin{aligned}
SV_h &\mapsto S_j V_h \\
SV_{-h} &\mapsto SV_{-h}
\end{aligned}$$

that is, a simple palatalization.¹⁹

There seems to be a circular motivation here. The phonotactics requires that palatalization must happen, but palatalization happens only to satisfy the phonotactics! This is a clear example of “conspiracy” in the sense of Kisseberth (1970). In simple terms, a rule is motivated merely to satisfy a constraint, so there must be some “conspiracy”.

There is nothing conspiratorial if we view this process as a repairing process. Take the input element type to be $V_h + V_{-h} + S + S_j$, and define the step function as

$$\begin{aligned}
f(S, V_h) &:= \text{inj}_2 S_j \\
f(S_j, V_{-h}) &:= \text{inj}_2 S \\
f(x, _) &:= \text{inj}_1 x
\end{aligned}$$

Now, the output element type τ is $(V_h + V_{-h} + S + S_j) + (S + S_j)$. By collapsing the output element type, we reach $\mathcal{C}[\tau] = V_h + V_{-h} + S + S_j$; this is precisely the output element type for the transducer.

¹⁸Note that glides are conventionally analyzed as vowels due to the phonotactics.

¹⁹Or seen as an instance of “underspecification”.

By converting the output element type to a Boolean type, a recognizer for the phonotactics is instead obtained.

There are two interesting properties of this process. First, we can find another embedded transducer that encapsulates Archangeli’s (1988) idea of “underspecification”. For the transducer, it does not matter what the preceding affricate/fricative is as long as it is coronal. If we replace all occurrences of S and S_j in the input sequence with an arbitrary symbol S' , the input element type becomes $S' + V_h + V_{-h}$. S' can be viewed as an “underspecified” coronal affricate/fricative. Second, the embedded transducer is idempotent. This means that a repaired sequence *cannot* be further repaired, or in other words, must be accepted by the embedded recognizer. This seems to be an intuitive condition on repairing processes.

Definition 6. A function f is *idempotent* iff $f \circ f = f$, or in other words, $\forall x. f(f(x)) = f(x)$.

More research is needed to clarify the properties of such processes. From this short example, however, it is easy to see how type theory can help us better understand the intimate connection between rules and constraints. In this case, both rules and constraints seem to reflect a more generalized notion.

3.6 From Models to Types to Automata

It should be briefly mentioned how the three-way correspondence between model-theoretic, type-theoretic, and automata-theoretic formalizations works. The correspondence between models and types is apparent for anyone who has worked with logical transductions. A logical transduction maps a model to another model, in which the crucial part is the predicates. The predicates are responsible for uniquely picking out the terms, so they (or some combinations of them) pretty much directly correspond to types. If the logical transduction for a strictly k -local function is “canonicalized” by requiring that every conjunction must have k conjuncts that talk about the k input elements, then we end up with a step function defined in a weird way.

For example, the running example of bounded tone shift in Rimi (Section 2.2) can be defined as the logical transduction

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma'(x) &:= \sigma(\text{pred}(x)) \wedge _ (x) \\ \acute{\sigma}'(x) &:= \acute{\sigma}(\text{pred}(x)) \wedge \sigma(x) \\ ?'(x) &:= \acute{\sigma}(\text{pred}(x)) \wedge \acute{\sigma}(x)\end{aligned}$$

where $_ (x) := \top$. It must be possible to canonicalize any “linguistically relevant” logical transduction this way—this implicit metaconstraint is what makes our type-theoretic, that is, propositional-logical formulation possible at all.

The correspondence between types and automata is also apparent. Consider bounded tone shift again. Omitting the states for INIT, the machine is

which has the state transition function δ defined as, in a curried form,

$$\begin{aligned}\delta(\sigma, \sigma)(\sigma, \sigma) &:= (\sigma, \sigma) \\ \delta(\sigma, \sigma)(\acute{\sigma}, \sigma) &:= (\sigma, \acute{\sigma}) \\ \delta(\sigma, \acute{\sigma})(\sigma, \sigma) &:= (\acute{\sigma}, \sigma) \\ \delta(\sigma, \acute{\sigma})(\acute{\sigma}, \sigma) &:= (\acute{\sigma}, \acute{\sigma}) \\ \delta(\acute{\sigma}, \acute{\sigma})(\sigma, ?) &:= (\acute{\sigma}, \sigma) \\ \delta(\acute{\sigma}, \acute{\sigma})(\acute{\sigma}, ?) &:= (\acute{\sigma}, \acute{\sigma}) \\ \delta(\acute{\sigma}, \sigma)(\sigma, \acute{\sigma}) &:= (\sigma, \sigma) \\ \delta(\acute{\sigma}, \sigma)(\acute{\sigma}, \acute{\sigma}) &:= (\sigma, \acute{\sigma})\end{aligned}$$

The reader is welcome to verify that it is indeed possible to derive the state transition function from the step function. Remember that the second argument of δ is the input–output pair.

4 Discussion

Type theory is a very different metatheory than set theory. This is especially true as we have taken an *intuitionistic* (or more generally, constructive) view of type theory, as is the formulae-as-types interpretation.²⁰ Such interpretation is inherently intuitionistic, because it induces an inherent relation between logic and construction. Crucially, this amounts to an inherent relation between logic and *computation* when computation is considered a

²⁰There is a confusing use of Church’s (1940) simple type theory as the basis of higher-order predicate logic. This is apparently *not* the formulae-as-types interpretation, as is not the Montagovian view. Under such a view, types are not formulae and must be supplemented with a semantics.

constructive act. The emphasis is put on the act of constructing and manipulating proofs, rather than the ad hoc notion of truth.

A type-theoretic approach can make certain things more naturally expressible. For example, the idea in Section 3.4 is so natural in a type-theoretic setting, but can only be established as an afterthought in a set-theoretic setting. The author thinks this is not a coincidence, but is a consequence of the fundamental difference between the two metatheories.

A point worthy of emphasis is that set theory per se does not provide a semantics. Indeed, a logical transduction defined in predicate-logical terms is meaningless by itself. For it to make sense, the logical formulae must be interpreted in a *model*, which in turn is understood by people who use them. In contrast, types arise *from the semantics*. This is evidenced by the fact that each type is characterized by its introduction and elimination rules, which specify precisely how to arrive at a proof and what consequences to draw from the proof. This proof-theoretic nature of type theory is not only philosophically important, but also practically important.

Beside philosophical interests, the author hopes that type theory can contribute to the more ambitious grand scheme of *direct* computational interpretations of linguistic theories. That is, linguistic theories, at least the intuitions behind them, should be directly interpreted in a practical computational system. In the course of doing so, unattainable assumptions can be found and vague theoretical notions be clarified. Now, even the most fundamental notion of *features* suffers from a severe degree of vagueness. For example, what is the exact nature of linguistic features? In what ways are features used? Why should the distinction between privative and binary features matter? The list of research questions goes on. Once we reformulate the ideas in type-theoretic terms, we can hopefully provide a better, or at least alternative view.

Even in this very simple (pun intended) study of strictly local functions, there are some interesting open questions that are intentionally left unaddressed. Representation-wise, only immediate, linear adjacency is captured in our notion of strict locality, but strict locality can be “relativized” in some sense, such as in tier-based strict locality (Heinz et al., 2011). Moreover, how should we formulate autosegmental representations in our terms? In turn, how do these representations interact and

compose? Process-wise, considering “recursive” strictly local functions is also crucial for modeling spreading and similar processes. More things can be done and should be done.

One last remark should be made on the “order-preserving” metaconstraint, which roughly specifies that the transduction must preserve the order of terms, that is, the input–output association must not have crossing line. This metaconstraint is implicit in Figure 1, as the correctness of the implementation at all should show. It is, however, impossible to state this correctness condition *within* a simple type theory, because it requires types to depend on terms, specifically terms with an order. This use of (dependent) type theory for program verification is a fascinating topic, but is also out of the scope of this paper.

5 Conclusion

This paper has argued for a type-theoretic formulation of strictly local functions. Specifically, strictly local functions can be formulated in a simply-typed λ -calculus as typed λ -terms. When viewed under the formulae-as-types interpretation, this resonates with the idea that strictly local functions correspond to quantifier-free logical transductions. None of the ideas is new, but the adaptation itself is novel.

The simply-typed formulation helps clarify some notions. For example, some forms of “conspiracy” and “underspecification” can be considered as instances of embedding in the so-called “repairing” strictly local functions. More generally, the author believes that type theory is an excellent metatheory for computational interpretations of linguistic theories, and hopes that this paper can serve as the first step in the grand scheme.

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```

let make_lsl2 init step =
  let rec loop t1 outs = function
    | [] -> outs
    | t2 as t1' :: ins' ->
      let outs' = Snoc (outs, step (t1, t2)) in
      loop t1' outs' ins'
  in
  function
  | [] -> None
  | t1 :: ins ->
    let outs = Snoc (Lin, init t1) in
    Some (loop t1 outs ins)

```

Figure 5: A definition of left strictly 2-local function maker

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A An OCaml Implementation

It has been claimed that Figure 1 can be directly implemented in a programming language. Here is such an implementation in OCaml.²¹ OCaml is used specifically for its polymorphic variants, which serve more conveniently as the element types given their structural (as opposed to nominal) nature. Bounded tone shift in Rimi (Section 2.2) will be used again as a toy example.

Because bounded tone shift, as analyzed in this paper, is *left* strictly local, we use **Snoc** lists to accumulate the elements “in reverse”. They are just **Cons** lists with a reverse argument order.

²¹OCaml is a modern descendant of ML. See <https://ocaml.org/> for more information.

```

type 'a tsil =
  | Snoc of 'a tsil * 'a
  | Lin

```

Given this type, a (polymorphic) left strictly 2-local function *maker* can be defined as in Figure 5, parameterized by *init* and *step* functions. Note that the resulting strictly 2-local function returns 'a tsil option values, because it is otherwise undefined for the empty list []. The *init* and *step* functions for bounded tone shift are easily defined and passed to the *maker* to produce the desired strictly local function.

```

let bts_lsl2 =
  let init _ = `S
  and step = function
    | (`S, _) -> `S
    | (`HS, `S) -> `HS
    | (`HS, `HS) -> `Q
  in
  make_lsl2 init step

```

Let us check that the three cases are all handled correctly.

```

let _ =
  [[`S; `S; `S];
  [`HS; `S; `S];
  [`S; `HS; `S]]
|> List.map bts_lsl2

```

They are indeed handled correctly (run the code to see!). This is just a toy example, but it shows cases what the implementation should generally look like.

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